

NEW PEDAGOGICAL APPROACHES IN WORKING WITH INCLUSIVE AND STAGED CLASSES

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Abstract. *To study the content and essence of normative and regulatory laws and by-laws adopted to ensure that students with special educational needs receive equal education as their healthy peers, and the theoretical and practical significance of teaching inclusive education in primary and higher education and ways to organize joint education of students in differentiated classes, regardless of their physical, intellectual, social, emotional, language, and other characteristics. Support through modern pedagogical approaches is the main goal of socializing children. The implementation of ways to support inclusive education through differentiated, differentiated approaches through established norms and documents is the demand of the day. This article shows that in inclusive education, all students are provided with the same educational environment, with the aim of meeting each individual need, coherence, purposefulness, decision-making, the main role of special educators in organizing this education, as well as opinions and discussions about differentiated education are expressed.*

Keywords: *project, team, student, inclusive education, differential, approach, classroom, pedagogical views, socialization, documents, demand.*

Introduction

As you know, we have set ourselves the principle
that the state serves the people.

You are also a worthy member of our society.

We will create all conditions for this area.

Every person in Uzbekistan is valuable to me.

President of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Sh.M. Mirziyoyev

The process of development of society is associated with the revision of the education system. Changes in society also require adjustments in the direction of education and upbringing. The use of new forms and methods of teaching is gradually becoming a progressive force in the development of society. Based on this, innovation is of great importance in the restructuring of society. Innovation is a continuous process, an integral part of pedagogical activity. On the basis of innovative pedagogical views, today our state and society are carrying out reforms aimed at fully ensuring the rights of children in the field of education and their socialization. A number of normative and regulatory laws and by-laws are being adopted to ensure that students with special educational needs receive equal education as their healthy peers, including: Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, adopted on April 30, 2023, September 23, 2020, Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" No. 3PYK-637, January 7, 2008, The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. URQ-139 "On Guarantees of the Rights of the Child", the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Approval of the Concept for the Development of

the Public Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030": Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-5712 of April 29, 2019, Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-60 of January 28, 2022 "On the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022–2026", Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-134 dated May 11, 2022 "On approval of the National Program for the Development of School Education in 2022–2026", Resolution No. PQ-4963 of January 25, 2021 "On measures to support research activities in the field of public education and introduce a system of continuous professional development", The Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-4860 "On measures to further improve the system of education for children with special educational needs" approved the concept of developing inclusive education in the public education system for 2020-2025.

Also, the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 638 dated October 12, 2021 "On approval of regulatory legal acts on the education of children with special educational needs" was adopted. Resolution No. 740 of the Cabinet of Ministers of November 24, 2025, introduced many changes in the field of monthly salaries in the education sector. In particular: The procedure for dividing the staff units "Special Pedagogue" and "Assistant Teacher (Assistant Teacher)" in general education schools has been clearly defined; Special educators will be paid a 50 percent bonus compared to their official salary; For teaching students who are taught individually at home, including 2 or more students of the same age and at the same address, teachers of general education schools will be paid a monthly travel allowance in the amount of one time the base calculation amount; The salary of a paid position of "assistant teacher" is calculated by multiplying the minimum wage by a coefficient of 2.470.

The purpose and objectives of the topic:

Teaching inclusive education in primary and secondary education, that is, ways to organize the education of students together, regardless of their physical, intellectual, social, emotional, language and other characteristics. Inclusive education (English: inclusion - inclusion, inclusion in education, joint education) has the meaning. It is a form of education in which every person, regardless of their physical and intellectual, social, emotional and linguistic background, as well as race and color, is given the opportunity to study in general education institutions. Supporting the needs for inclusive education and the advantages of this form of education through modern pedagogical approaches based on adopted regulatory documents is the main goal of the socialization of children.

The implementation of ways to support inclusive education through differentiated, differentiated approaches through established norms and documents is the demand of the day. Exclusion - children with disabilities who are not included in education, that is, outside of education. Such children are not involved in education and their rights to education are not automatically ensured. Segregation - separating children with special needs from general education and providing them with education in special schools and boarding schools. Integration - organizing separate classes in general education schools for children with special needs. Inclusion - children with special needs studying in the same class with other children in general education schools.

Relevance of the topic: These decrees and resolutions identify the need to find solutions to a number of problems facing the education system:

1. The shallowness of the regulatory framework in the field of inclusive education.

2. The high need for training qualified teachers for the inclusive education system and continuous development of their inclusive competence.

3. Ensuring the continuity and consistency of inclusive education in preschool educational organizations, general secondary and secondary specialized education, vocational education, and higher education systems. The high need to strengthen the material and technical base of institutions where inclusive education is introduced;

4. Insufficient scientific and methodological base for teachers and educators in inclusive educational institutions, that is, the necessary literature, methodological manuals.

5. High level of provision of a safe inclusive educational environment, etc. Solving these problems creates the basis for the successful process of education, upbringing, development, and socialization of each child with individual educational needs. In particular, the training of pedagogical personnel is one of the main issues.

Because it is precisely because of the human factor that the education system moves and develops or, conversely, faces a crisis. The implementation of inclusive education in practice automatically creates an increase in the demands placed on the activities of teachers and educators, the need to expand their functional responsibilities and professional qualifications. Traditional knowledge and skills alone are not enough in this type of education. Working with children in need of special assistance requires special professional competence from teachers and educators, that is, inclusive competence.

It should be noted that in order to form inclusive competence, *a teacher must possess such important qualities as empathy, reflection, mobility and flexibility, the ability to collaborate, sensitivity to the needs of learners, sociability, and self-management skills.*

Expected result: Works taking into account the psychological aspects of education for students with special educational needs. Inclusive education is a form of education in which every individual, regardless of physical and intellectual, social, emotional and linguistic background, as well as race and color, is given the opportunity to study in general education institutions. To create a barrier-free, adapted educational environment for students with special educational needs at school, using special tools and methods, involving special educators, organizing differentiated classes, and providing quality general secondary education that serves the effective adaptation and full integration of children into society. Inclusive education is an educational process leading to the development of an inclusive society, which is a historical process that goes through exclusion, segregation, and integration.

Research materials and methodology

Specific features of the inclusive education system in Uzbekistan

The strategic goal of state education policy - to increase the availability of quality education that meets the requirements of innovative economic development, the modern needs of society and each citizen - is associated with creating an educational environment that ensures the successful socialization of all students, regardless of their psychophysical condition and development.

Inclusive education is a process of education and upbringing in which all children, regardless of their physical, mental, intellectual and other characteristics, are included in the general education system. They study with their non-disabled peers in mainstream schools in the community, taking into account their special educational needs. Including or encompassing all services, facilities or objects that are usually expected or required. Specialised education - children with physical and mental disabilities in special (correctional) institutions of types I-VIII; integrated education - children in special classes (groups) in educational institutions; inclusive education -

when children with special educational needs are taught in the same classroom as ordinary children. The process of developing general education, which provides for the accessibility of education for all, including children with disabilities.

Chapter 7, paragraph 44 of Resolution No. 638 of the Cabinet of Ministers states the idea of organizing a comprehensive examination of students and the activities of a psychological-medical-pedagogical council.

Statistical data: Today, more than 15% of the world's population is made up of people with disabilities. Taking into account their families, friends and loved ones, we can say that disability problems affect 50% of the population. There are 810,000 people with disabilities in Uzbekistan. Today, they are disadvantaged, facing all forms of discrimination: at school, at work and in family life. Models of disability: 1. Historical or religious-moral model; 2. Medical model; 3. Social model.

“Inclusive education is the education of children with disabilities, mental and physical developmental disorders, together with their healthy (normative) peers in general education institutions.” Inclusive education, which is rapidly entering the practice of general education institutions, poses many complex issues and new tasks.

Requirements for inclusive education: Equality of opportunity; Barrier-free environment; Systematicity; Availability of a resource teacher; Accurate diagnosis; Public awareness.

The regulatory and legal framework of inclusive education - in accordance with the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, children with special educational needs should be educated in educational organizations according to the general education curriculum and an individual (individual) program. The regulatory and legal framework of special and inclusive education - international laws, the legislative framework of the Republic of Uzbekistan, documents containing the regulatory framework for special and inclusive education.

Search results

The structure of inclusive education in Uzbekistan: inclusive education - Preschool educational institutions, general education schools, resource centers, lyceums, colleges, higher educational institutions; Rehabilitation centers Logopoints. Educational and methodological support for the activities of teachers working in inclusive education: Development of methodological recommendations; Conducting practical seminars, master classes, webinars, establishing systematic cooperation with educators; Exchange of experience between teachers and educators of special and general education organizations; Analysis and generalization of the best educational practices. Scientific and methodological support of the educational process in inclusive education: Development of educational and methodological support - State standards, curricula, curricula, educational and methodological guidelines, Methodological recommendations and manuals. Recommendations for including children with special needs in inclusive education: Accept students with disabilities as much as possible; Include them in the same activities as all children, with a separate approach; Involve children with special educational needs in group work using an individual approach; It is necessary to create special educational programs for children with special educational needs using ICT in the educational process.

The project “From Inclusive Education to an Inclusive Society” was implemented at the competition for state social orders announced by the Public Fund for Support of Non-Governmental Non-Profit Organizations and Other Civil Society Institutions under the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The purpose of this project is to develop a mechanism for inclusive

education for children with Down syndrome and autism who have undergone cochlear implantation surgery, and to create psychological and methodological training technologies for working with children.

Target groups of the project - children with Down syndrome; children who have undergone cochlear implantation surgery; children with autism spectrum disorders. 3 different mechanisms for introducing inclusion in general education schools for children with Down syndrome and autism spectrum disorders were proposed. Mechanism I Children of this type study in the same class as their healthy peers, but educational, correctional and developmental goals and tasks are implemented on the basis of a special and appropriate curriculum, an individually structured program and didactic support, and the child is necessarily accompanied by a special educator. 3 - mechanism (social inclusion). Children of this type receive education in a correctional class organized at a general education school, but in some subjects (for example, music, visual arts, physical education, technology, natural science) it is recommended to participate in the lessons of these subjects with healthy peers in the classroom with the accompaniment of a special educator, and in school and extracurricular activities they are together with their normally developing peers in the school community. Stages of involving children with KI, Down and autistic symptoms in inclusive education:

Initial stage - 1. Organization of the learning environment. 2. Use of a visual table. 3. Priming (Priming (priming effect, fixed setting)) - in psychology, it represents a hidden memory mechanism that provides an unconscious and involuntary influence of some stimuli on the processing of subsequent stimuli. Priming manifests itself in a change in the speed or accuracy of responses to subsequent stimuli or in the spontaneous increase in the first stimulus under appropriate conditions. In this case, it is necessary to distinguish between the effect itself, in fact, priming, and the resulting changes in the speed or efficiency of stimulus processing, the so-called priming effects.

Disputes

The role and importance of collaborative pedagogy in working with inclusive and differentiated classes in pedagogical activity

Article 36 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education", approved on September 23, 2020, states: "Experimental and innovative activities in the field of education are carried out with the aim of modernizing education and are aimed at developing new educational technologies and resources, testing them and introducing them into the educational process." And we will achieve this through innovations in education. One of the important requirements for teachers and educators is to teach young people in inclusive and differentiated classes to think independently through a deep understanding and application of innovations in the field of education. Developing practical foundations for the use of modern pedagogical and innovative technologies in the organization of the educational process and effective ways to use them is one of the urgent issues facing the education system. In implementing these works, it is of particular importance that teachers of continuing education, especially teachers and special educators teaching inclusive classes, have sufficient professional qualifications, work on themselves, and be aware of the best practices of pedagogy. In this regard, it is important to know the essence and ideas of the views of cooperative pedagogy and use them. The ideas of cooperative pedagogy are today embedded in the content of pedagogical technologies and form the basis of the "21st Century Education Concept". Cooperative pedagogy is integral and interconnected with humanistic

pedagogy. Cooperative pedagogy has long been used in the education systems of developed countries.

In the research of Simon Lvovich Soloveitchik, one of the founders of the idea of cooperative pedagogy, a new approach to the issue of upbringing is emerging, in which upbringing begins to be expressed not as some kind of influence of the educator on the child, but as an open relationship between the teacher and the student.

Cooperative pedagogy is close to “creative pedagogy” in its “creativity” nature. According to pedagogical innovators, cooperative pedagogy should accept any child as a natural child. In this case, the teacher helps the child to maintain his individuality and awakens the motivation for his intellectual and moral development. The following can be cited as the main ideas of cooperative pedagogy:

- teaching the child in the zone of proximal development:
- teaching without coercion:
- teaching based on basic words, schemes, symbols:
- the idea of progression:
- the idea of large blocks:
- the idea of free choice:
- the idea of dialogic thinking:
- the idea of the intellectual environment of the classroom:
- the idea of cooperative activity of students and teachers:
- the idea of the voluntariness of leisure activities.

Cooperative educational technology aims to form a worldview based on the development of intellectual, spiritual-moral and physical abilities, interests, and motivations in students with health and special educational needs.

Cooperative pedagogy is an independent pedagogical concept, the main result of which is the achievement of the intended goal in the cooperation of the student and the teacher. Cooperative pedagogy is an education that represents the joint mastering of knowledge, mutual development, and the joint organization of the “student-student(s)”, “pedagogue-student(s)” relationship during the learning process.

The main idea of cooperative pedagogy is to complete educational tasks in a team, small groups or pairs together, in cooperation with each other. "Cooperative pedagogy" is considered an educational technology according to its level of application: general pedagogical, according to its philosophical foundations: humanistic, according to its approach to the child: personal-humanistic, subject-subject (cooperation), and according to the application of methods: problem-research, creative, dialogic, and game-based.

As principles of cooperative learning technology:

- mutual unity of members of a pair and small group;
- responsibility of each member of a pair and small group for personal and group success;
- organization of cooperative learning activities in a small group;
- general assessment of group and team work.

As signs of cooperative learning technology, we can indicate the following:

- attention to the student's personality, individuality;
- development of independent and critical thinking in students;
- ensuring the emergence of a positive attitude towards the teacher and peers;
- development of cultural communication skills in students;

- creation of an environment based on cooperation and mutual equality.

Conclusion. From a pedagogical point of view, cooperation contributes to the formation and manifestation of new qualitative changes in the activities of the subjects of the educational process. An important aspect of pedagogical cooperation is that it serves to harmonize the activities of the subjects of the educational process, both inclusive and differentiated classes, as well as healthy children. In the process of pedagogical cooperation, the activities of the teacher and the student are harmonized, acquire a creative character, which requires taking into account each specific aspect of the activities of the subjects of the educational process.

Cooperation in the "teacher-student" relationship is organized on the basis of the idea of a joint analysis of the course and results of this activity, the socialization of the child, sincerity to each other in the spiritual world, strong mutual understanding, and the joint developmental activity of adults and children. In the pedagogical process in traditional education, the participation of the teacher as a subject and the student as an object changes, and the student-student participates as a subject of activity. The "teacher-student" relationship is realized in such types of cooperation as joint participation, joint care, joint creation, and joint management.

Technologies for developing inclusive education as part of updating educational content **Inclusive education** is a process of education and upbringing in which all children, regardless of their physical, mental, intellectual and other characteristics, are included in the general education system. They study with their peers without disabilities, taking into account their special educational needs, in mainstream schools in society: including or covering all the services, means or objects that are usually expected or required; differentiated education is children with disabilities in special (correctional) institutions of types I-VIII; integrated education is children in special classes (groups) in educational institutions; the process of developing general education, which provides for the accessibility of education for all, including children with disabilities; inclusive education is when children with special educational needs are educated in a classroom with ordinary children.

It is necessary to pay attention to the strategic stages of engagement in inclusive education:

1. Stages of search and engagement.
2. Stages of dealing with children with special needs.
3. Stages of rehabilitation.
4. Stages of integration.

Use of interactive technologies - Children with disabilities are usually not encouraged to learn. But information technologies can solve this problem. Bright colors, movement, sound effects - these are factors that keep the child's attention for a long time, help to make the learning process more conscious. The use of interactive technologies in the educational process, along with traditional teaching methods, significantly increases the effectiveness of education. For NBB, an interactive whiteboard is a visual tool, along with sound and video effects.

Using a "magic" pen and pointer not only develops the child's logic, creative thinking, motor skills and coordination, but also allows him to go back, see where mistakes were made, analyze his work.

The main distinguishing feature of a multimedia interactive whiteboard is the ability to control objects by touching the surface of the whiteboard - move them, increase or decrease their size, rotate, underline with a marker, play sound, video, launch WEB pages, delete or clone them.

Creating a successful situation, minimal fatigue, increasing interest in learning are clear indicators of the effectiveness of using interactive equipment in school. An interactive whiteboard will become an indispensable assistant in the classroom, a great addition to the vocabulary and an assistant in learning. This allows for a wider use of visual aids in studying the material, so the presented material will be understandable to students.

Features of each interactive form in inclusive education –

Creative task: “A creative task (especially practical and close to the student’s life) gives meaning to learning, motivates students. The uncertainty of the answer and the ability to find your own “right” solution, based on your personal experience and the experience of your colleague, friend, allow you to create a basis for cooperation, joint learning, and dialogue of all participants.

Working in small groups – this type of training allows the student to “practice cooperation, interpersonal communication skills”: “active listening, developing a common opinion, resolving disagreements that arise”. The teacher should form in the students’ ideas about the rules of working in a group. This can be done, in particular, with the help of a memo containing the following points: “be honest with your comrades, work as much as you can; listen carefully, without interrupting, to each member of the group; speak briefly, clearly so that everyone can speak; support the other, despite intellectual differences.

Role-playing - The purpose of role-playing games is a method of teaching, developing and educating schoolchildren in an interesting, playful, creative way. "In role-playing games, real-life situations are staged and various behavioral models are played, then discussed and recommendations are given. The goals of developing communication skills, behavior and managing emotions are achieved."

Mini-lecture - A mini-lecture is a short, clear speech that provides an explanation of principles, models, theoretical positions, research results, and considerations that may be important for the current educational needs of students.

Lecture rules

1) if the theoretical material is presented according to the principle of "from general to specific", then the principle of scientific specificity should be used (for reference to authoritative sources);

2) the teacher should present all the material in a convenient way, taking into account the age characteristics of the students;

3) after the lecture, the student must have feedback;

4) the lecture material must have a practical orientation.

PAMN-formula: The PAMN-formula (position - basis - example - result) is a rapidly developing technique that allows you to activate student activity. The PAMN formula is actively used in organizing disputes and discussions, contributing to the development of students' not only analytical skills, but also the ability to reason, independently find confirmation of their assumptions and prove their point of view.

Training - this form of interactive education is aimed at developing "skills and abilities in any field through the performance of sequential tasks, actions or games aimed at achieving and developing the necessary skills."

Block-modular training is one of the main technologies that ensure the formation of students' competencies in the classroom. The teacher takes an individual approach to students, which leads to an increase in interest in the subject.

A project is a set of search, research, calculation, graphic and other types of work carried out by students independently, but under the guidance of a teacher, in order to solve an important problem, either practically or theoretically. The role of the teacher in interactive education - In interactive education, teachers not only perform educational and professional roles, but they also

- designers,
- programmers,
- diagnosticians,
- researchers,
- organizers,
- managers,
- innovators,
- teachers and
- consultants.

Therefore, teachers are both the organizers of the entire educational process and themselves, communication partners for the student. An interactive teacher is a teacher who respects all students, listens to them and helps them solve problems independently. The teacher's posture and behavior are given the same importance, as is the teacher's work with children. An interactive teacher is a teacher who knows and understands some basic principles related to how a child learns, and at the same time can use different forms and methods of teaching to help all children.

The direct participants in interactive education are, of course, teachers and students, but school principals and specialists (teachers, psychologists, defectologists, speech therapists, tutors) also play an important role in organizing interactive education. Thus, the researchers included school principals, educational managers, and teachers in the questionnaire and questionnaire. To the question "To what extent is interactive education used in educational work with school-age children?", the participants in the training gave the following answers:

D-1: It is easier for teachers to work in a traditional way, so they rarely practice interactive teaching.

E-2: Interactive teaching is carried out by more experienced teachers who know how to use this type of teaching.

D-5: Interactive teaching is more common in preschool institutions than in the first grade of primary school.

D-7: Some teachers, despite their training and qualifications, do not use interactive teaching.

D-8: Interactive teaching is not used sufficiently in our schools, firstly, the curricula do not leave room for interactive teaching; secondly, school textbooks are more adapted to the traditional teaching style.

D-9: Working in groups requires special tasks developed separately for each group, and therefore it is difficult for teachers to develop various tasks.

Often, the lesson plan does not allow for the use of interactive educational technologies.

Analysis of the survey results allowed us to develop the following recommendations for teachers.

- Any topic can be interactive, but it takes more time to prepare for the lesson;
- The interactive teaching method should not be considered and studied only when it is a research goal;

- It is necessary to organize joint meetings with teachers and hold open conversations and discussions on the importance of interactive teaching;
- It is necessary for teachers to visit each other's classes and exchange experiences;
- It is necessary to develop instructions for the teacher
- Thus, interactive teaching has many advantages over the traditional teaching method, and therefore it should be used more often by teachers.

Factors ensuring the effectiveness of inclusive and differentiated education

Today, preparing the younger generation for life in modern society requires determining the psychological, emotional, physical and social readiness of the student at different stages of education in general education institutions. These requirements can be implemented with a differentiated approach to the goals and content of correction, that is, the qualitative level of diversification through a stratified (differential) approach to students creates the need for a different system. This situation leads to the strengthening and complexity of differential preparation according to the student's abilities, interests, and mastery - a global trend of the modern school.

The strategic goal of state education policy - to increase the availability of quality education that meets the requirements of innovative economic development, the modern needs of society and each citizen - is associated with creating an educational environment that ensures the successful socialization of all students, regardless of their psychophysical condition and development.

Consilium (Latin consilium - council) means. Pedagogical consilium is a type of expert assessment method; it involves a collective discussion of learning outcomes according to a specific program and general principles, a collective assessment of certain aspects of the personality, and the identification of the causes of deviations that occurred in the process of forming certain characteristics of personality traits. A council is one of the methods of work of a psychological service, a collective decision of persons participating in educational work on the formation of a pedagogical diagnosis and the development of measures of pedagogical influence on the student. By a council we mean a constantly working, coordinated group of specialists united by common goals, implementing one or another strategy for monitoring the child. In such a team, it is necessary: based on the order of the school principal, a Council is formed, consisting of the following: Deputy Director for Academic Affairs (Chairman of the Council); Deputy Director for Spiritual and Educational Affairs (Deputy Chairman of the Council); teachers of inclusive education classes and primary basic correctional classes; psychologist; special educator; tutor; pediatrician (psychoneurologist), nurse.

Also, the school principal and his deputy for educational affairs shall supervise the timely conduct of classes and the implementation of curricula; specialists who are not available at the school may be involved in the work of the Council on a contractual basis; parents of students or their substitutes may participate in Council meetings; the Council shall hold meetings at least once a quarter of the academic year on the development of students, implementation of curricula, health and psychological state; The requirements in accordance with the content and essence of paragraphs 43-48, such as the Council shall submit a proposal to the psychological-medical-pedagogical commission to remove a student from an inclusive education class or primary correctional class based on the student's learning, implementation of the curriculum, health, and psychological state, are also coherently emphasized and qualified with analytical concepts in this chapter. The ability of the entire pedagogical team to understand and comprehend the essence of the existing problems of students further strengthens the resulting effectiveness. Thus, the

pedagogical council, by its very nature, is considered the most important section of mental health work, and if it is thoroughly thought out, planned and implemented by a qualified psychologist and special educator, it allows for the solution of many problems.

In the cases I have observed, the listeners are advised to read Chapter 5 of this Resolution: Paragraphs 20, 21, 26, 27, 28, 31 on the organization of the educational process in inclusive education classes and primary basic correctional classes; Chapter 6: Paragraphs 34, 36, 38, 40, 41, 42 on the activities of pedagogical staff and cooperation with parents; It is clear that we need to be more consistent and united in our approach to ensuring the implementation of Chapter 8: Financing and Logistics, paragraphs 52, 53, 54; and Chapter 9: Final Provisions, paragraphs 55 and 58.

The role of the pedagogical team and special educators in the education of students studying in inclusive classes

The tasks of the pedagogical team working with students with special educational needs, in addition to the tasks that must be performed by the above-listed teachers, require responsibility for performing additional tasks. The pedagogical team working with children with special educational needs is a team consisting of special educators, defectologists, speech therapists, psychologists and other specialists, who aim to provide quality education and upbringing to children with disabilities or various developmental limitations.

Defectologist - studies the mental or physical development of a child, develops correctional programs. **Speech therapist** - helps children with speech problems, identifies speech defects and conducts classes aimed at correcting (correcting). **Psychologist** - studies child psychology, analyzes the mental state of children, forms motivation, helps solve emotional problems. **Class teacher or educator** - organizes daily educational work. **Special educator** - assists the main teacher in an inclusive classroom, conducts extracurricular activities with students with special educational needs.

Correctional and developmental practical exercises (sample)

These exercises can be used by a teacher, defectologist, speech therapist, psychologist or parents when working with children with special educational needs in the areas of speech, movement, attention, memory, sensory-emotional areas.

1. Exercises that develop attention and perception

Exercise: "Find the difference"

Materials: 2 similar but different pictures (with 10 differences)

Task: The child finds the differences between the two pictures.

Purpose: To develop concentration, thinking.

Exercise: "Where is it hiding?"

Materials: 5-6 objects are placed on the table, then the top is covered.

Task: After the cover is closed, the child answers the question "Which object is missing?"

Purpose: To develop visual memory and observation.

2. Development of speech and phonemic hearing

Exercise: "Find the sound in the word"

Task: The child hears and says the letters "a", "s", "m" from the word spoken by the teacher.

Objective: To develop phonemic perception, to teach to distinguish sounds.

Exercise: "Word chain"

Task: The teacher says "bread", the child says a word starting with the last letter of this word - "n" ("cannabis", "what", etc.).

Objective: To increase vocabulary, to develop logical speech.

3. Sensory development exercises (sensory integration)

Exercise: "Touch"

Materials: Soft, rough, cold, warm, round, oblong objects

Task: The child closes his eyes and identifies the given object by touch.

Goal: Develop sensory sensitivity and sensory differential perception.

Exercise: "Let's draw in the sand"

Materials: Sand tray, stick

Task: Letters, shapes, drawing

Goal: Develop tactile perception, motor skills and imagination.

4. Development of fine and gross motor skills

Exercise: "Let's make a picture from shapes"

Materials: Cut geometric figures of different colors and shapes (circle, square, triangle).

Task: The child creates a house, tree, man and other objects from these figures.

Goal: Develop motor skills, coordination and creative thinking.

Exercise: "Let's string"

Materials: Large beads, thread

Task: The child strings beads on a thread according to their color or shape.

Goal: Develop fine motor skills and coordination.

Conclusion and recommendations

Methodological recommendations and advice

- The role of parents in inclusive education: inclusive education is an approach ensures that children with disabilities and various individual needs study and learn together with other children in the general education system. It creates conditions for children to become active participants in society, to fully integrate into the life of society. The active participation of parents in this process is very important. They not only provide a home environment for the child's development, but also, in cooperation with educational institutions, create a comfortable and supportive environment for the child.

The following recommendations will help you with this:

1. Take an active part in your child's life;
2. Support your child at home;
3. Help him/her adapt socially
4. Celebrate successes,
support him/her in failures;
5. Understand and
accept your child's capabilities;
6. Teach your child to be independent;
7. Develop yourself as well;
8. Adapt the home environment;
9. Exchange experiences with other parents;
10. Prepare your child for socialization.

Psychological recommendations for a responsible and effective approach

1. Regard the child's abilities with trust and love;
2. You too should avoid drawing wrong conclusions and
comparing the child with others;

3. Celebrate even the small achievements of your child

- this will increase his self-confidence;

4. If you feel tired or difficult, do not hesitate to consult a qualified psychologist.

Recommendations for eliminating obstacles: Introducing per capita financing in the education system; Training and improving the skills of teachers and leaders; Increasing teachers' salaries, paying additional salaries; Equipping institutions (ramps, special educational rehabilitation, medical and equipment elevators, specially equipped learning spaces); Raising public awareness of inclusive education; Working with parents.

Specific forms of practical assistance –

- Individualized Education Plan - Should be developed in collaboration with teachers and specialists.
- Motivating children - Building confidence through leading questions, encouragement, and praise.
- Teaching through play - Building academic and social skills through play.
- Reading together - A way to encourage reading and develop speech.
- Using digital tools - Special platforms, audio materials, apps, and programs.

In conclusion,

By creating a scientific base for inclusive education in Uzbekistan, developing methodological developments, innovative approaches and international experience exchanges, and ensuring stability, inclusive education will become a single principle of general education in the future, enriched on the basis of technological and pedagogical innovations, the human dignity of every child will be recognized and respected, and a stable, equal and comfortable environment for learning will be created.

In conclusion, it should be noted that the formation of inclusive competence in preschool and general secondary school educators and pedagogical staff is a complex, continuous and systematic process. In this regard, the following levels of attention should be paid to the training of modern personnel working in an inclusive educational environment:

1. Adherence to the principles of continuity and interdependence in the implementation of inclusive education;

2. The problem of inclusive education is a problem faced not only by future defectologists, but also by future primary and preschool teachers, and the content of inclusive education should be more widely included in the content of pedagogical disciplines in the curriculum of these areas;

3. Incorporating modern theories of inclusive education into educational practice, creating conditions for future primary and preschool teachers to master the basics of person-oriented approaches in teaching;

4. To involve senior students of primary education and preschool education of higher educational institutions as tutors (assistant pedagogical staff) in general education institutions where an inclusive education system has been introduced during the pedagogical practice period;

5. It is necessary to develop pedagogical, psychological, methodological literature, manuals, recommendations and programs that will help teachers and educators create a safe inclusive educational environment for children in need of special assistance.

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